

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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IDENTIFYING GAPS IN THE PREVENTION OF
CATHETER-ASSOCIATED URINARY TRACT INFECTION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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May 2021

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4784677

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this quality improvement project was to determine the gaps between published evidence-based practice (EBP) guidelines and clinical practice related to indwelling urinary catheter (IUC) care and the prevention of catheter-associated urinary tract infection (CAUTI) based on healthcare professionals (HCP) perspective. A CAUTI is a urinary tract infection (UTI) related to an IUC that has been in place for more than two days. CAUTI accounts for 40% of hospital-acquired infections, increasing the need for continued prevention. The number of CAUTI events in the project ICU was consistent with the national and community data. An investigation of practice was conducted in two Medical Intensive Care Units (MICU) in a Level I Trauma Center hospital in California. Participants included registered nurses, nursing assistants, and physicians. Participants completed a Fishbone (Ishikawa) tool, a Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats (SWOT) Analysis survey, and the Center for Disease Control and Prevention Targeted Assessment for Prevention (TAP) survey to identify underlying causes, prevention strategies, and IUC care. Results from the surveys confirmed gaps between published guidelines and current clinical practice. Causes of CAUTI related to HCP practices, IUC care, and inconsistent prevention practices were identified. Barriers that impede CAUTI prevention efforts and HCP perceptions must be considered when addressing areas for improvement. Understanding the local context and culture can maximize organizational resources and improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections, CAUTI, Evidence-based Guidelines, Fishbone (Ishikawa), Strengths, Weaknesses, Threats, and Opportunities (SWOT) Analysis, Targeted Assessment for Prevention (TAP)

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am so thankful to my wonderful family for being there for me throughout the Doctorate of Nursing Practice (DNP) journey. I am dedicating this DNP project to my dearest husband, Dr. Stephen Puentes. He encouraged me to fulfill this DNP as one of my dreams and has been amazingly helpful, supportive, and loving all the time. He is my superhero. I want to thank my two beautiful daughters, Samantha and Christina, and my siblings, specifically Dr. Florence Chong, for their support and understanding. I am fortunate that my mother, Leticia, led the way and shared the importance of education.

I want to thank those who supported me during the entire DNP journey. A heartfelt thanks to Dr. Rachel McClanahan as my Team Leader, who has been phenomenal. She provided guidance, support, and encouragement. I am so grateful to Dr. Beverly Quaye for her positive feedback and guidance. I am very thankful to Dr. Paul Holtom, Dr. Timothy Botello, and Dr. Lucine Huckabay for their confidence in my abilities to succeed in this endeavor. My sincere thanks to Dr. Brad Spellberg, Dr. Allison Luu, the Intensive Care Unit leadership, the unit nurse managers and supervisors, champions, and team members as well as the Information Systems Department for making this project possible despite the COVID 19 pandemic. I am thankful to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention for technical assistance and all my friends and relatives for being there for me.

Background

Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infection (CAUTI) events remain a challenge despite prevention practices (Meddings et al., 2014). CAUTI is a urinary tract infection (UTI) associated with indwelling urinary catheters (IUC), specifically with those in place for more than two days (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2020; Regagnin et al., 2016). CAUTI accounts for approximately 40% of all hospital-acquired infections (HAI), despite the availability of national prevention guidelines (Galiczewski & Shurpin, 2017).

The use of IUC for the inpatient population ranges from 12% to 25% (Tyson et al., 2018). Patients with IUCs are at a 3% to 10% risk of developing UTI per day of catheterization (Gupta et al., 2017; Tyson et al., 2018). Eight to twenty-one percent of UTIs occur in the intensive care unit (ICU), and approximately 80% to 95% are directly related to IUCs (Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Regagnin et al., 2016). While some patients need an IUC due to urinary retention or strict fluid monitoring, up to 50% of IUCs in the U.S. are not medically necessary (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], 2020; CDC, 2020; Meddings et al., 2014; Parker et al., 2017). The incidence of CAUTI can be prevented by decreasing inappropriate use of IUCs and immediate removal when no longer indicated (Meddings et al., 2014).

Developing a CAUTI can lengthen a patients' hospital stay from 10 to 106 days (Alexaitis & Broome, 2014). In 2016, the cost of a CAUTI event ranged from \$600 to \$20,000. The economic impact to the U.S. health care system from CAUTI is \$3 to \$4 billion annually (Tominaga et al., 2014; Tyson et al., 2018). A growing concern is multidrug-resistant organisms, such as extended-spectrum beta-lactamases and carbapenem-resistant *Klebsiella Pneumonia* in patients with IUC (Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Meddings et al., 2014).

To reduce preventable HAI, healthcare funding and monitoring agencies enacted regulations to reduce CAUTI. In 2008, the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid (CMS) announced a halt in reimbursements for costs incurred due to CAUTI (Gupta et al., 2017; Hollenbeak & Schilling, 2018; McNeill, 2017; Tominaga et al., 2014). The CMS further constrained underperforming hospitals with high CAUTI incidents through a negative incentive program of penalty in Medicare funds (Purvis et al., 2017). In 2011, to receive full reimbursement, CMS required acute care settings to report CAUTIs to the CDC's National Healthcare Safety Network [NHSN] (Tominaga et al., 2014; Yokoe et al., 2014). The Joint Commission (TJC) emphasized the need to educate healthcare workers, patients and their families to reduce CAUTI in its 2012 National Patient Safety Goals. The Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS) set forth a national goal to decrease CAUTIs in ICUs by 25% in 2020 (Alexaitis & Broome, 2014; Gupta et al., 2017).

The CDC and the Society for Healthcare Epidemiology of America (SHEA), in collaboration with the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA), developed evidence-based practice (EBP) guidelines to reduce CAUTI. Guideline recommendations include indications for IUC use, an aseptic technique for catheter insertion, proper IUC care, maintenance, and timely removal, and these are collectively known as CAUTI prevention bundles (Ballard, 2018; CDC, 2020; Tominaga et al., 2014). Some hospitals use multifaceted CAUTI prevention strategies, including educational programs, reminder checklists, nurse-driven protocols, where nurses can perform catheter removal based on a set of markers, without the need for physician's order or leadership rounds (Galiczewski & Shurpin, 2017; Shea et al., 2019; Tyson et al., 2018). Other strategies to prevent CAUTI include using alternatives to IUC,

external devices, such as condom catheters, external female catheters, and intermittent catheters (Lo et al., 2014; Gray et al., 2016; Maehle et al., 2017).

Local Context

A 600 bed Los Angeles County academic medical center has noted variations in CAUTI events every month, beginning in 2016. The highest CAUTI events occurred in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU), consistent with the literature (Alexaitis & Broome, 2014; Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Leticia-Kriegel et al., 2019). In 2018, there were 43 CAUTI events hospital-wide, 34 in the ICU, and nine in the medical-surgical wards. In 2019, there were 34 CAUTI events hospital-wide, 29 in the ICU, and five in the medical-surgical wards. After the November 2019 skills day and audit interventions, CAUTI events decreased significantly in the Medical ICU (MICU), from two to zero in November 2019 through March 2020. However, in the Pediatric ICU, CAUTI events increased to one in January from zero in 2019.

In 2020, amid the COVID-19 pandemic, the CAUTI events and other metrics related to IUC increased facility-wide. In 2020, total CAUTI events were 40, with one to six events recorded each month from January through December. The higher burden of CAUTI occurred in two MICU. Compliance for IUC audited in the ICU included a collection bag, not touching the floor, less than two-thirds full, catheter secured, red seal intact, and tubing free from obstruction was 100%. Hospital-wide compliance audits of perineal care, which includes cleansing the urethral meatus, was 84%. Documentation of catheter care having been performed every 12 hours averaged 89% in all ICUs. Finally, the facility continues to have higher than the expected national benchmark, Standard Infection Ratio (SIR) of over 1.0. The SIR is a metric used in surveillance to measure performance against similar facility types (CDC, n.d.; Purvis et al.,

2017). A SIR of fewer than 1.0 means performing better than expected (CDC n.d.; Purvis et al., 2017).

A CAUTI committee was established in 2016 and a task force in 2019 to examine, implement, and improve practices and strategies to reduce events. Several changes were implemented based on committee or task force recommendations. For the insertion phase, alternatives to IUC such as condom catheter, intermittent catheter, and Purewick, a new female external catheter, was introduced in 2019. Other newer products were explored as needed. For the maintenance phase of IUC, perineal care audits were implemented in 2019; however, these were discontinued in 2020 due to COVID-19. Compliance with hand hygiene was emphasized, and monitoring this activity was delayed briefly but resumed in June 2020. Standardization of perineal care task time per unit had been underway in 2019-2020; however, it was delayed due to priorities related to COVID-19. For the removal phase of IUC, daily rounds on patients with IUC, reminder calls to MDs, and continued implementation of the nurse-driven protocol were all emphasized. Still in progress is a design upgrade of the electronic order of IUC that automatically prompts renewal or discontinued use after the designated time.

Other interventions were implemented to reduce CAUTI facility-wide, including staff huddles, nurse-driven protocols, audits and feedback, screensavers, email reminders, web pages, educational programs on proper IUC insertion and maintenance, and changes to the urinalysis reflex ordering system. Individual units also implemented various strategies, including having designated health care personnel perform chart audits, nursing assistants charged with performing perineal care, and a two-person insertion team.

Problem Statement

The project hospital's clinical units are not meeting standard benchmarks for eliminating CAUTI events, despite implementing prevention strategies. There is a lack of hospital-wide standardization in prevention practices.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this quality improvement (QI) project was to identify the gaps between published evidence-based guidelines and current clinical practices to determine barriers, facilitators, and strategies to reduce CAUTI. The objectives are to identify:

1. significant and underlying causes of CAUTI events,
2. strengths, weaknesses, threats, and opportunities for CAUTI prevention,
3. the level of awareness, knowledge, and perceptions of HCP related to IUC and CAUTI prevention in two MICUs.

The project will help identify current prevention practices to provide recommendations for EBP strategies, which can bridge the gaps between practice and research to reduce CAUTI events. There is an assumption that the project facility complies with regulations, meets benchmarks, and improves practices to obtain better patient outcomes (McNeill, 2017; Purvis et al., 2017).

Supporting Framework

Once it is determined that an improvement in practice is needed, a framework or model for change is adopted to provide a process for evaluating the changes implemented. A framework is used to outline the steps necessary to develop a change to meet the desired outcome, such as increasing patient safety (AHRQ, 2020; Reed & Card, 2016; Scoville & Little, 2014). The Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) designed the Model for Improvement (MFI), which

centered on implementing practice changes to improve a system (Scoville & Little, 2014). The MFI has two components, the three questions and the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycle (Provost & Murray, 2011).

Figure 1

Model for Improvement

Note: PDSA Framework: IHI, n.d.

The MFI uses the PDSA cycle to refine processes when implementing a change (IHI, n.d.; Provost & Murray, 2011; Scoville & Little, 2014). Several studies have shown that PDSA cycles demonstrate healthcare practice improvements (Bollegala et al., 2016; Knudsen et al., 2019; Maxwell et al., 2018). The PDSA cycle's key features are an iterative process that uses continuous data collection and testing on a small scale to measure improvements (Knudsen et al., 2019). The PDSA has four stages or steps to implement change for improvement, as shown in Figure 1 (Bollegala et al., 2016; IHI, n.d.; Scoville & Little, 2014).

To answer the first question, "*What are we trying to improve,*" investigators would first need to determine baseline CAUTI measures and gaps in the use of EBP guidelines in practice. The second question, "*How can we measure that a change has occurred,*" has to do with how the intervention will be measured (Provost & Murray, 2011). In this project, the changes in CAUTI events and adherence to developed protocols will be determined after the recommendations are adopted and implemented. The final question of the MFI is, "*What intervention can achieve an improvement*" (Provost & Murray, 2011). Based on the project results, gaps and priority interventions will be determined and recommended for implementation.

Plan Stage

In the Plan stage, a problem was identified, a purpose statement was developed, a method of evaluation was determined, and a timeline was established (IHI, n. d.; Scoville & Little, 2014). Stakeholders were identified and engaged as they were essential to organizing and implementing the project surveys (IHI, n.d.; Scoville & Little, 2014). Existing literature regarding national guidelines, such as those provided by the CDC, identify prevention strategies, policies and procedures, education, and competency resources to address CAUTIs were examined. An assessment of the current practices was necessary to understand better and tailor specific interventions to improve CAUTI events.

Do Stage

In the Do stage, the plan was carried out. "Do" means deliberately conducting, performing, or implementing the methodology planned to address a problem (IHI, n.d.; Scoville & Little, 2014). Data were collected (IHI, n.d.). Survey promotion plans and procedures were implemented to ensure that the project aims were achieved (Deming, 1994; IHI, n.d.). Success in conducting the surveys relied heavily on collaboration, communication, and coordination

between the project lead and stakeholders (Bollegala et al., 2016). A Fishbone and SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) Analysis and Targeted Assessment for Prevention (TAP) surveys were conducted to gather data regarding CAUTI prevention practices.

Study Stage

The Study stage involved reviewing, analyzing, and interpreting the collected data (Bollegala et al., 2016). Fishbone, SWOT, and TAP results were calculated to determine the frequency of responses to each question. Barriers, facilitators, and a better understanding of gaps to implementing CAUTI prevention strategies were identified and reflected in lessons learned (IHI, n.d.). Current practices in IUC management and CAUTI prevention were compared to the EBP guidelines to determine gaps and strategies to address those gaps. A set of recommendations is provided to stakeholders to determine the next steps (Scoville & Little, 2014).

Act Stage

The Act stage is the last cycle, whereby the decision to alter, abandon, adopt, or implement another PDSA cycle was made (IHI, n.d.). If the outcome desired has been achieved; then, the new strategies will be included as part of the comprehensive approach to patient care to prevent CAUTI. A revision of the current plan, expansion of the new successful program to other areas, or both occur during this stage. If the result or outcome was not met, the project is modified, and a new PDSA cycle was initiated, or the project is abandoned (IHI, n.d.; Knudsen et al., 2019; Scoville & Little, 2014). If another cycle is needed, preparation for that is started during this stage.

Review of Literature

The purpose of this project is to identify the gaps between published evidence-based guidelines and current clinical practices to determine barriers, facilitators, and strategies to reduce CAUTI in a southern California healthcare facility. The objectives of the project are to:

1. Identify significant and underlying causes of CAUTI events,
2. Identify strengths, weaknesses, threats, and opportunities for CAUTI prevention,
3. Identify the level of awareness, knowledge, and perceptions of HCP related to IUC and CAUTI prevention in two Medical ICUs.

The project will help identify current prevention practices to provide recommendations for EBP strategies, which can bridge the gaps between practice and research to reduce CAUTI events. There is an assumption that the project facility complies with regulations, meets benchmarks, and improves practices to obtain better patient outcomes (McNeill, 2017; Purvis et al., 2017).

A literature review was conducted to obtain research related to CAUTI pathogenesis, risk factors, barriers, evidenced-based guidelines, and transforming evidence-based practices. Databases searched included CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and OneSearch using the following terms in various combinations, "catheter-associated urinary tract infection," "CAUTI," "evidence-based practice," "prevention," "best practice," "intervention," "strategies," "risk factors," "contributing factors," "barriers," "facilitators," "adherence," "compliance," and "gaps". Articles selected for review were published outside of and within the U.S. from 2010 to 2020, peer-reviewed, used various methodologies and were written in English. Duplicates, abstracts, posters, and articles about non-acute care settings, long-term care, and nursing homes were excluded.

Definition of CAUTI

A CAUTI is a urinary tract infection caused by an IUC inserted via the urethra, left in place beyond recommended guidelines. An IUC consists of tubing and a drainage bag (CDC, 2020). Intermittent catheters, nephrostomy tubes, ileoconduits, and suprapubic catheters are not IUCs (CDC, 2020). The CDC (2020) NHSN established the criteria for CAUTI as an IUC that has been in place for greater than two days, with 100,000 CFU/ml of microorganisms other than yeast or candida, fever of > 38.0 among patients who are 65 years or older. The patient must also have one of the following symptoms of UTI: Suprapubic tenderness, costovertebral pain or tenderness, urinary frequency, or dysuria (CDC, 2020). Upon abstraction of data from the electronic health record, CAUTI is determined based on the CDC criteria and reported to NHSN.

Pathogenesis

A UTI develops when microorganisms enter the bladder from the perineum via the urethra. The microorganisms are typically from the patient's gastrointestinal tract, such as *Escherichia coli*, or those found on the skin (Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Gray, 2010). Other microorganisms that can cause UTIs in patients in the ICU include *Enterobacteriaceae*, *Enterococcus*, and *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* (Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Gray, 2010).

Pathogens commonly found in the urethral area can be resistant to more than one class of antibiotics known to cause symptomatic UTI.

During IUC insertion, pathogens can enter the urinary tract through the catheter-urethral lumen interface or catheter lumen. Up to 66% of CAUTIs are due to the urethral lumen interface, and 34% are due to the intraluminal migration of microorganisms to the bladder related to manipulation of the urinary drainage system (Gray, 2010; Gyesei-Appiah et al., 2020). When an IUC is introduced in the urethra, a biofilm of microorganisms develops in the catheter's internal

lumen and external surfaces, causing infection (AHRQ, n.d.; Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Gray, 2010). The catheter interferes with the body's natural defense mechanisms that prevent microorganisms from migrating into the bladder, putting the patient at risk for infection (Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Gray, 2010). The biofilm spreads to other urinary catheter and urinary tract epithelium surfaces, leading to infection and potential antibiotic resistance (Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Gray, 2010).

Risk Factors Associated with Developing CAUTI

The most common risk factor for CAUTI development is the prolonged placement of an IUC (AHRQ, n.d., CDC, 2020; Leticia-Kriegel, 2019; Lo et al., 2014; McNeill, 2017; Meddings et al., 2014). While any patient with an IUC is at risk for developing CAUTI, there are nonmodifiable and modifiable risk factors that put some patients at greater risk (Gray, 2010; Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Leticia-Kriegel et al., 2019). Nonmodifiable risk factors are characteristics inherent to the individual, such as being female, pregnant, over 50 years old, with diabetes mellitus, or other comorbidities (CDC, 2015; Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Gray, 2010; Hollenbeak & Schilling, 2018).

Modifiable risk factors are those conditions that can be changed, such as duration of the IUC placement, lack of aseptic catheter technique, IUC insertion over six days during the patient's length of stay, IUC insertion outside the operating room, and poor nutrition (Chen et al., 2013; Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Gonzalez & Sole, 2014; Gray, 2010; Gupta et al., 2017). A common modifiable factor that can result in a CAUTI is poor hand washing, which is an example of a lack of aseptic technique and is attributed to 15% of infections (Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Leticia-Kriegel et al., 2019).

Critically ill patients in the ICU with comorbidities are at the most significant risk for developing a UTI, causing CAUTI event numbers to be higher among that patient population (AHRQ, n.d.; Alexaitis & Broome, 2014; Park et al., 2018). In the ICU, prolonged catheterization accounts for 95% of UTIs and 16.5% of CAUTIs (Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; Leticia-Kriegel et al., 2019). A root cause analysis found that 25% of CAUTIs were preventable had the IUC been removed early (Leticia-Kriegel et al., 2019).

Healthcare Cost of CAUTI and Return on Investment

CAUTIs are cost-intensive and can cause a significant financial burden to a healthcare organization due to extended hospital stay and limited reimbursements from CMS and third-party payors (AHRQ, n.d.; Chenoweth & Saint, 2013; O'Neill et al., 2018; Quinn, 2015). A single event's cost can range from \$600 to \$3000, with the total costs to a healthcare organization multiplied by the number of patients with CAUTIs per month (Ferguson, 2018; Richards et al., 2017; Tyson et al., 2018). While financial outlay is a priority, the pain and suffering among patients with CAUTI is the most significant concern.

The return on the investment must be considered when addressing how CAUTIs are prevented. Return on investment refers to the amount of money invested in prevention strategies, compared to the gains from investment in decreased CAUTI-related costs. While interventions to prevent CAUTI might be expensive, the cost of not investing those dollars can be much higher. An organization's culture, leadership, buy-in and engagement by HCP, and commitment to dedicate resources depend on the value placed on EBPs used to prevent CAUTI (Scanlon et al., 2017; Underwood, 2015). Organizations that consider CAUTI a priority and allocate adequate resources have seen positive outcomes including, decreased length of stay, reduced re-admissions, increased patient and HCP satisfaction, and overall cost savings (Conner et al. 2013;

Fakih et al., 2014; Fletcher et al., 2016; Meddings et al., 2014; Quinn, 2015; Scanlon et al., 2017; Shea et al., 2019).

Evidence-Based Clinical Practice Guidelines

In response to the increase in CAUTI events, several national agencies developed EBP guidelines designed to target practices and improve prevention. The CDC, the Society for Healthcare Epidemiology of America (SHEA), the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA), the Institute for Health Improvement (IHI), and the Association of Professionals in Infection Control and Epidemiology (APIC) have all developed CAUTI prevention guidelines with variations in priorities and recommendations. Guidelines provide a clear set of practices designed to ensure standardized practice (Jordan et al., 2017). The CDC Healthcare Infection Control Practices Advisory Committee (CDC HICPAC) is the leading source for guidelines to prevent HAIs, such as CAUTI (Meddings et al., 2019). While key recommendations from each of the published guidelines will be discussed, the CDC HICPAC guidelines, referred to as CDC guidelines, will be the primary reference for this project.

CAUTI prevention guidelines from the CDC have been widely used and have IUC elements rated 1B in the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) criteria (Carr et al., 2017; Fakih et al., 2014; Meddings et al., 2019). The GRADE criteria determine the quality and strength of the evidence used to develop the recommendations, with 1A being the highest scientific clinical or statistical significance level and strategies rated at 1B having been shown to reduce CAUTIs (CDC, n.d.; Jordan et al., 2017; Lo et al., 2014; Meddings et al., 2019).

The CDC guidelines focus on the proper use of IUCs, aseptic technique with insertion, proper maintenance, surveillance, quality improvement, and infrastructure components necessary

to strengthen preventive measures (Lo et al., 2014; Underwood, 2015). The guidelines include the following recommendations: proper hand hygiene, barrier precautions for insertion, use of the smallest gauge catheter, securing the catheter properly, obtaining urine samples aseptically, replacing the system if a break in aseptic technique or disconnection occurs, and the importance of training the patients and family (Lo et al., 2014).

The CDC and IDSA both recommend evaluation of alternatives to IUC, regular review of the indications for IUC, use of aseptic technique and sterile equipment, routine hygiene for meatal care, maintaining a closed drainage system, and avoiding irrigation (IHI, 2011; Lo et al., 2014; McNeill, 2017). The IDSA/SHEA (2014) shared the recommendations of preserving a closed collection system, avoiding routine irrigation, having trained personnel insert the catheter, and maintaining the collection bag below the bladder level.

The Institute for Health Improvement [IHI] (2011) developed the four components of IUC care to prevent CAUTI. The components were avoiding unnecessary IUC, insert urinary catheters using aseptic technique, maintain catheters, daily review of urinary catheter necessity, and prompt IUC removal when no longer indicated (McNeill, 2017). The IHI (2011) further indicated the need to form a team, set aims, use the Model for Improvement, and have process and outcome measures.

In providing guidance, the American Nurses Association (ANA, n.d.) adopted the CDC guidance of using an IUC only for specific reasons, assessing daily for continued use, and providing appropriate maintenance care. The ANA (n.d.) provided additional guidance and a shared algorithm for nurse-driven protocol, removing an IUC when no longer indicated without a physician's order. The ANA and the CDC recommend limited use of urinary catheters and immediate removal when no longer indicated (Meddings et al., 2014; Park et al., 2018).

Alternatives to IUC

A commonly used alternative to IUC placement is intermittent catheterization. Intermittent catheterization is a single-use device that can empty the bladder when patients cannot drain their bladder independently (Alexaitis & Broom, 2014; Meddings et al., 2014). Intermittent catheterization allows the patient to have greater mobility and takes two to three minutes to perform than an IUC insertion time of 15 to 20 minutes (IHI, 2011). A bladder scanner, commonly used in the ICU, allows the assessment of urinary retention and assists in decision-making regarding the need to insert an IUC (Alexaitis & Broome, 2014; Lo et al., 2014; Mara et al., 2011; Meddings et al., 2014). Intermittent catheterization with bladder scan is beneficial as they pose no patient harm and can reduce catheterization rates by 30% to 50% (IHI, 2011).

Other alternatives to IUCs are external collection devices (ECD), which are placed or adhered to the outside of the genitals to collect urine; these include condom catheters, male and female urinals, and wicks (Gray et al., 2016). Like an intermittent catheter, ECDs allow patient mobility and show lower bacteriuria rates and lower catheter utilization rates (Eckert et al., 2020; Gray et al., 2016).

Indications for IUC Use

The CDC recommends that IUCs should be used mainly for patients who are critically ill needing an hourly urine output measurement, those with urinary retention or obstruction, patients with urinary incontinence with stage III or IV open sacral or perineal pressure injury, immobilized patients with the thoracic or lumbar spine injury, those having had surgical procedures, or patients receiving end-of-life care (AHRQ, n.d.; CDC, n.d.). Since the

recommendations limit the numbers and types of patients who need an IUC, alternatives should be considered.

Catheter Size, Type, and Standardized Kits

Before IUC insertion, the size and type of catheter and standardized IUC kit should be considered (Lo et al., 2014; Marra et al., 2011). The recommendation is to use the smallest IUC size to minimize trauma and reduce the possibility of CAUTI (CDC, 2019; Lo et al., 2019; Marra et al., 2011). Catheters are made of latex, silicone, and silver-coated or antibacterial material. The use of impregnated silver-coat IUC did not show statistical significance in decreasing CAUTI (CDC, 2019; Lo et al., 2014; Marra et al., 2011; Meddings et al., 2014). Antimicrobial- or antiseptic-impregnated catheter use is recommended only after prevention strategies have not adequately decreased the CAUTI rate (CDC, n.d.). Having standardized kits available to assist HCP in performing IUC insertion in an organized manner is recommended to avoid errors, such as a breach in aseptic technique (CDC, n.d.; Lo et al., 2014).

Aseptic Technique of IUC Insertion

An essential strategy to reduce CAUTI is the IUC insertion technique to prevent bacteria introduced into the bladder, which can cause a UTI (CDC, 2019; Meddings et al., 2014). The risk of CAUTI can be reduced from 17% to 69% by using proper infection prevention measures (CDC, n.d.; Clayton, 2017; Galiczewski & Shurpin, 2017). Preventive measures recommended related to IUC practices are the use of proper hand hygiene, aseptic technique, avoidance of contaminated IUC with urethral drainage, as well as having HCP don personal protective equipment, such as gowns and gloves, and using sterile drapes (CDC, 2019, 2020; Clayton, 2017; Galiczewski & Shurpin, 2017).

A two-person IUC insertion with protocol and algorithm can reduce the CAUTI rate from 2.24 to 0 per 1000 catheter days (CDC HICPAC, 2019; Fletcher-Gutowski & Cecil, 2019; Galiczewski & Shurpin, 2017; Lo et al., 2014; Meddings et al., 2014; Yokoe et al., 2014). With the two-person insertion team, one HCP observes, and the other inserts the IUC, and the procedure is halted if the insertion technique is compromised (Fletcher-Gutowski & Cecil, 2019; Galiczewski & Shurpin, 2017). Two-person insertion, coupled with other prevention strategies, showed lower contamination, increased awareness, improved patient safety, and reduced costs (Fletcher-Gutowski & Cecil, 2019; Galiczewski & Shurpin, 2017).

Proper Maintenance and Care of IUC

All HCP must be familiar with proper maintenance and care of an IUC, which includes positioning, meatal care, proper urine specimen collection to prevent infections, and technique for transport of patients with IUC (AHRQ, n.d.; Greene, 2020; HICPAC, Lo et al., 2014; Panchisin, 2016; Yokoe et al., 2014).

Positioning

Guidelines advise securing the catheter collection tube to the thigh to prevent it from moving, pulling, or kinking (CITATION). Positioning the drainage bag below the bladder helps avoid the reflux of the urine to the bladder, which can cause UTI (Clayton, 2017; Green, 2020; Tyson et al., 2018). If it is necessary to break the closed system, an aseptic technique should be used, or the IUC should be replaced with a new device to avoid microorganism growth (CDC, n.d.; Clayton, 2017; Greene, 2020; Tyson et al., 2018).

Meatal Care and Hygiene

The CDC guidelines address challenges related to perineal care, including cleaning the periurethral area during a bed bath and avoiding the use of antiseptics when a patient has an IUC

(CDC, n.d.; Lo et al., 2014). The 2014 Compendium of Evidence showed no significant difference between antiseptics, such as chlorhexidine or povidone-iodine, and non-antiseptics and found that washing with soap and water was sufficient (Fasugba et al., 2016; Greene, 2020; Lo et al., 2014; Meddings et al., 2014). Perineal care should be performed immediately after incontinence (Lo et al., 2014). In fecal incontinence cases, the recommendation is to use containment devices to prevent further spread of the microorganisms (CDC, n.d.; Greene, 2020; Lo et al., 2014).

Proper Urine Specimen Practices

The CDC (2019) recommends obtaining urine samples aseptically by disinfecting the IUC needleless sample port before urine collection and avoiding contamination. Using a sterile syringe or cannula adapter to aspirate a small sample from the port and avoiding irrigation prevents microorganism growth (Clayton, 2017; Greene, 2020; Lo et al., 2014; Tyson et al., 2018). Large urinalysis volume should be obtained aseptically from the drainage bag (CDC, n.d.). The standardization and improvement in urine collection practice as a part of the multiple strategies showed a decrease in IUC utilization of up to 90% and CAUTI rate of 87.5%, with sustained zero CAUTI in one of the studies (Davies et al., 2018; Maxwell et al., 2018).

Techniques for Transport of Patients with IUC

When transporting a patient with an IUC, the drainage bag must be emptied using a clean collection container. The drainage spout must not touch any objects to keep the urinary catheter system from contamination to prevent infection (CDC, n.d.; Lo et al., 2014).

Immediate Removal of IUC

Immediate removal of the IUC when no longer indicated is key to minimizing the prolonged duration that causes most CAUTIs (ANA, n.d.; CDC, n.d.; Meddings et al., 2014;

Park et al., 2018). The CDC HICPAC recommends using reminder systems to identify patients with IUCs and conducting assessments to determine the continued need for indwelling catheterization (CDC, n.d.; Chen et al., 2013; Clayton, 2017; Meddings et al., 2014). Constant awareness, communication, and tracking of patients with IUC are essential when an electronic system is not available (CDC, 2019; Clayton, 2017; Lo et al., 2014; Meddings et al., 2014; Tyson et al., 2018). Indication for use and the date and time of insertion should be documented (CDC HICPAC, n.d.; Clayton, 2017). Healthcare personnel, particularly nurses, should use the handoff as an opportunity to exchange patient information about IUC care and duration, for assessment follow-up of, and determination of possible removal (Clayton, 2017).

Bundles

The catheter-associated urinary tract infection (CAUTI) 'bundles' effectively reduce harm in the unit (Carr et al., 2017). CAUTI bundles are a set of evidence-based infection prevention practices that, when implemented collectively, can improve HCP compliance, patient outcomes and create a standardized process for providing care (Ballard, 2018; CDC, 2020; Tominaga et al., 2014). Healthcare organizations implement bundled strategies because a single intervention is not enough to prevent CAUTIs (Metroyanis & Gargan, 2019).

Bundles, combined strategies, can be related to insertion, care and maintenance, and removal of IUC. Various combination of strategies, such as reminders or checklists, which can be used during rounds, huddles, or as audit monitoring tools by champions to ensure tasks in caring for IUC after placement, showed to be effective in CAUTI reduction (Carr et al., 2107; Metroyanis & Gargan, 2019). In addition, an IUC maintenance bundle includes the performance of hand hygiene upon patient contact, and daily meatal hygiene with soap and water, assessment and documentation of the continued need for an IUC, intact tamper-evident seal, securement of

the device, use of a clean container when emptying the drainage bag, maintenance of unobstructed urine flow, and action to discontinue IUC when no longer indicated (Ballard, 2018; CDC, 2020; Tominaga et al., 2014). In addition, the ABCDE bladder bundle is frequently used by healthcare organizations and includes A) adherence to necessary preventive measures, hand hygiene, aseptic insertion, proper maintenance, education, surveillance, and feedback, B) bladder scanner to avoid IUC use, C) condom catheters or alternatives to IUC such as intermittent catheterization, D) do not use IUC except when indicated, and E) early IUC removal with a reminder or nurse-driven protocol (Meddings et al., 2014; Saint et al., 2014).

Summary

Catheter-associated urinary tract infections are common in the healthcare setting. Many healthcare organizations continue to see high levels of CAUTI events. Patients' risk factors predispose them to have infections, and barriers exist in CAUTI prevention practices. Guidelines are available to minimize patient harm; however, healthcare costs will increase tremendously when practical actions are not addressed. The project will address the need to determine the gaps between EBP in the literature and clinical setting practices. Efforts will be made to identify priorities and develop a set of recommendations for the design, implementation, and evaluation of EBPs to reduce CAUTI events at the project facility.

Methods

The purpose of this project was to identify the gaps between published evidence-based guidelines and current clinical practices to determine barriers, facilitators, and strategies to reduce CAUTI. The objectives were to identify:

1. significant and underlying causes of CAUTI events,
2. strengths, weaknesses, threats, and opportunities for CAUTI prevention,
3. the level of awareness, knowledge, and perceptions of HCP related to IUC and CAUTI prevention in two Medical ICUs.

The methods section described the project's setting, sample, design, procedures, data analysis, timeline, and ethical considerations.

Setting

The project facility was a 600 bed, level one academic trauma medical center located in Los Angeles, California. The project took place in two 20-bed MICUs (MICU A and MICU B). The MICU population consisted of critically ill patients with comorbidities that required medical interventions to stabilize their conditions and necessitate the need for IUC insertion and care. The two MICUs were designated as COVID positive cohort units.

Sample

Participants were HCP from the two MICUs, including nurse managers, nurse supervisors, registered nurses, a licensed vocational nurse, nursing assistants, attending physicians, and resident physicians. Participants were recruited regardless of years of professional experience in the unit or experience in the ICU setting.

Design

The QI project examined the practices related to IUC care, management, and CAUTI prevention practices and determined the causative factors, barriers and facilitators, awareness, and perceptions among HCP. The Fishbone electronic survey was used to gather and collect data from the participants' viewpoints to understand IUC management and CAUTI prevention practices. The participants provided information regarding their personal experiences related to IUC practices. The participants also responded to a SWOT Analysis and completed the TAP electronic surveys. Participants were encouraged to share their thoughts, perceptions, and knowledge related to current practices of IUC care and CAUTI prevention on each of these surveys. For each survey, participants completed demographic characteristics questions: work area/unit, work shift, age group, gender, highest educational level, length of time working in the area/unit, length of time in the position or role, and current professional position or role.

Procedure

Stakeholders

After approval of the project by IRB at California State University, Fullerton, the procedures were carried out as planned. The engagement of stakeholders was one of the first steps taken. Stakeholders included the Infection Prevention Chief Physician, Chief Quality Officer, Patient Safety Officer, ICU Chief Physician, MICU staff including Director Physicians, attending physicians, nurse managers, nursing assistants, and RNs of the two MICU units. Engagement and support from stakeholders were essential for planning, coordinating, and conducting QI activities. Communication and collaboration were keys to a successful QI initiative.

Participant Recruitment

Recruitment occurred through flyers posted around the MICU units, including the nursing station, physician workroom, and breakroom. Announcements about the project were also made during unit visits and through email notifications. Flyers contained information regarding the Fishbone, the SWOT Analysis, and the TAP surveys. The project survey links were emailed to potential participants. Surveys were completed by participants at their convenience using their own time during work, which allowed for ease in participation and potentially better representation of HCP. Participants were provided informed consent, and surveys took approximately 15 minutes to complete. The three surveys were conducted for 30 days to allow the highest number of responses.

Activity # 1 Fishbone Electronic Survey

The Fishbone, known as the Ishikawa, for its designer Kauro Ishikawa, is a widely used cause-and-effect analysis or root causes analysis tool for patient safety and quality improvement (Connelly, 2018; IHI, n.d.; Omar et al., 2020)). As a structured, visual tool, the Fishbone diagram helps determine the possible causes of a problem and the relationship between concepts, organized into meaningful categories through brainstorming (Connelly, 2018; IHI, n.d.). The head of the Fishbone diagram is the problem or concern that was being examined, in this case, increased CAUTI events (Connelly, 2018; IHI, n.d.). The "fish" has a central spine with additional spines running off the central spine, like branches of a fish's skeleton. The spines are organized into main categories, contributing factors to the problem (Connelly, 2018). The fish's bones branch off each main cause category, showing the deeper causes and linkages, which are the underlying causes, known as root causes.

Amid the COVID-19 pandemic, the in-person Fishbone was converted to an electronic survey format, using open and closed-ended questions. Closed-ended questions were developed based on factors known to contribute to CAUTI. Four main ‘spine’ categories, adapted from IHI, were people, process (methods), equipment (materials), and environment (IHI n.d.). In the last section of the Fishbone survey, respondents had an opportunity to provide information about other causes of CAUTI if none were applicable in the previous sections.

In the open-ended section, the “Five Whys” questioning process was used. Respondents were asked, “Why is this happening?” five times to elicit additional responses and broaden thinking about underlying causes and relationships (Connelly, 2018; IHI, n.d.). Respondents were provided a link to a three-minute video from IHI about how the Fishbone process works to minimize confusion and increase the survey's proper completion.

Activity # 2 Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) Analysis Survey

The SWOT Analysis is a strategic planning tool to improve programs or services within an organization focusing on implementation practices (Norwood et al., 2017; Vries-Erich et al., 2017). By looking at internal and external elements in a systematically organized way that influence the program or service, weaknesses and threats can be minimized, and strengths and opportunities maximized (Ansari et al., 2017; Norwood et al., 2017; Vries-Erich et al., 2017). Recommendations for improvement can be developed based on the data related to the SWOT categories. A SWOT analysis can help strengthen prevention practices and maximize resources to improve patient outcomes in a specific unit or entire facility.

The SWOT analysis was conducted using closed and open-ended questions to identify facilitating and impeding factors related to HCP practices in the MICU (Vries-Erich et al., 2017). The SWOT analysis utilized probing questions to help identify and explore the internal and

external forces within and outside the MICU, such as the strengths and weaknesses and the external opportunities and threats related to IUC practices and CAUTI prevention.

In conducting the SWOT Analysis, four open-ended questions were asked to elicit insights into IUC management and CAUTI prevention practices of HCP. The first question was to determine the unit's and HCP's strengths related to IUC management and practices to prevent CAUTIs. The second question was to determine weaknesses, which were aspects of the unit that interfered with implementation or training, collaboration, and communication or areas to be improved that address the IUC care and CAUTI prevention practices. The third question identified the opportunities, those external elements that facilitated and prevented CAUTI events that could improve current practices and reduce harm. The fourth question was to determine the threats, which were challenges in the system that contributed to interfering with the unit's or participants' application of the guidelines to IUC insertion, management, and care practices. The following open-ended questions were used to stimulate SWOT Analysis responses via survey for ideas and insights from the respondents:

1. What do you think are the strengths related to maintaining a zero CAUTI?

What do we do well?

2. What do you think are the weaknesses related to having CAUTI events?

What do we need to improve?

3. What are some opportunities related to IUC and CAUTI prevention practices?

What can we do that is not being done?

4. What are some threats to IUC and CAUTI prevention practices?

What obstacles are in the way of our CAUTI prevention efforts?

Activity # 3 Targeted Assessment for Prevention (TAP) Survey

The Targeted Assessment for Prevention (TAP) survey, developed by CDC (2016), is a gap analysis tool helpful in identifying self-reported awareness, knowledge, and perceptions of infection prevention strategies related to IUC and CAUTI by HCP (CDC, 2016; White et al., 2020). The TAP tool can help determine where the gaps exist to focus improvement efforts in those areas. The TAP can be used in a unit or an entire organization as part of the ongoing QI process (CDC, 2016; White et al., 2020). Any gaps, missing practice elements, are identified and targeted for improvement based upon the aggregated responses (CDC, 2016). The TAP survey consists of 49 questions, which were divided into six categories. The TAP survey required Yes, No, or Unknown responses in Category I. In Categories II through VI, a six-point Likert scale, with the number one indicating 'Never,' to five indicating 'Always,' and six for 'Unknown' (CDC, 2016). (CDC, 2016). The six categories were I. General Infrastructure, II. Appropriate Indications for Insertion, III. Aseptic Insertion, IV. Proper Catheter Maintenance, V. Timely Removal, and VI., Appropriate Urine Culturing Practices. Each section had a comment area for participants to provide additional information, ideas, or insights.

The TAP survey link was available to the respondents on the same day they completed the Fishbone and SWOT. The TAP survey was completed at the respondents' convenience and took approximately 15 minutes.

Data Analysis

The demographic survey described the participant's professional characteristics as aggregated data and represented both MICUs. Work shift, unit name and area, age, gender, professional role or position, length of time in the profession, length of time working in the unit,

and the highest education level, were calculated using descriptive statistics (see Table 2).

Demographic data was collected for potential use in designing targeted educational programs.

The Fishbone survey identified underlying causes of CAUTI. The frequency of responses to the Fishbone survey questions was calculated to determine possible underlying causes of CAUTI. The top five most frequent responses from both MICUs are shown in Figure 3. Responses to open-ended questions were organized into related categories and themes and described in the results section.

The SWOT survey responses were analyzed based on the frequency of responses in each category with aggregated data representing both MICUs. The frequency of responses and percentages are presented in Table 4. The open-ended SWOT Analysis responses are presented in Figure 4 with the recurring ideas identified under each heading S, W, O, and T and described in a narrative.

The TAP survey was analyzed based on the frequency of each category's responses related to the IUC and CAUTI prevention practices. The findings were compared to published EBP guidelines. Results determined existing gaps and helped identify priority areas for the development of practice change recommendations. The TAP survey summary responses are presented in Table 4. Respondents' comments are described in the results section narrative.

Ethical Considerations

The project was submitted and approved by the Institutional Review Board at California State University, Fullerton. There was no anticipated risk of harm related to participation. Participants provided informed consent when they clicked on "agree to participate" in any of the project's surveys. Participants were able to stop participating at any time. Participants' identities were protected and not tied to their responses to the surveys or demographic data. The survey

link was secure. The questionnaires resulted in aggregate data; no personal identifiers were used. Data collected will be destroyed after the completion of the project. Four \$25 Amazon gift card incentives were awarded for participation in all three surveys. Figure 2 shows the project timeline.

Results

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Participants completing the three surveys had similar demographic characteristics. Most were female, in the 39 to 54 age range, registered nurses with bachelor's degrees, who worked the day shift. The majority of the participants have been working in their current unit and position or role for over ten years, as illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristics	N=62 Fishbone		N=64 SWOT		N=111 TAP	
	Frequency (%)		Frequency (%)		Frequency (%)	
Current work location	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
4A	36	58%	38	59%	60	54%
4B	26	42%	26	41%	51	46%
Work shift						
Day	44	71%	43	67%	73	66%
Evening	2	3%	3	5%	7	6%
Night	16	26%	18	28%	31	28%
Gender						
Female	41	67%	44	69%	75	68%
Male	20	33%	20	31%	35	32%
Prefer not to disclose	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Age Group						
21-38	24	39%	27	44%	45	41%
39-54	28	46%	27	44%	54	49%
55 and over	9	15%	7	11%	12	11%
Highest level of education						
High school or equivalent	5	8%	4	3%	6	5%
Associate Degree	16	26%	12	7%	23	21%
Bachelor Degree	28	45%	37	67%	55	50%
Master Degree	4	6%	4	13%	10	9%
Doctorate or PhD	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Medical Degree	7	11%	4	0%	8	7%
Nursing Assistant Certificate	2	3%	3	0%	6	5%
Other	0	0%	0	0%	3	3%

Current role or position						
Registered Nurse	44	71%	49	77%	77	69%
Nursing Assistant	8	13%	8	13%	19	17%
Nurse Manager/Supervisor	3	5%	3	5%	6	5%
Physician-attending	1	2%	1	2%	1	1%
Physician-fellow	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Physician-resident	6	10%	3	5%	7	631%
Other	0	0%	0	0%	1	1%
Length of time in work area/unit						
< 1 year	8	13%	7	11%	18	16%
>1 year & < 5 years	11	18%	17	27%	24	22%
>5 years & <10 years	11	18%	11	17%	17	15%
>10 years	26	4194%	26	41%	44	40%
On rotation	6	10%	3	5%	8	7%
Length of time in position or role						
< 1 year	9	15%	6	9%	13	12%
>1 year & < 5 years	11	18%	13	20%	30	27%
>5 years & <10 years	10	16%	13	20%	18	16%
>10 years	30	48%	31	48%	48	43%
On rotation	2	3%	1	2%	2	2%

Note: Missing one respondent for Fishbone Gender (n=61) and Age Group (n=61); Missing three participants in SWOT total Age Group (62). HS=High School, LVN=Licensed Vocational Nurse

Fishbone Survey

For each item in the Fishbone, participants were asked to select which element related to categories, such as People, Method/Processes, Materials, Environment. For the People category, responses to the close-ended prompts pertained to any or combination of the specific discipline of causes of CAUTI related to nurses, physicians, or nursing assistants. If a participant did not think that the element applied to any of the people, they could select "Not Applicable."

Identified Causes Related to People

There was a total of 24 participants who did not perceive IUC and CAUTI as a priority. A cause related to nurses was lack of support and lack of empowerment. A lack of champions and forgetting to discontinue the IUC were selected as primary causes of CAUTI related to people/physicians. The lack of awareness and knowledge of IUC and CAUTI prevention and

skills competency based on the high-frequency response cause CAUTI related to people/nursing assistants (Table 2).

Responses to Open-Ended Five Whys Related to People

After each question in the Fishbone survey, participants were asked, "Why is this happening" multiple times to elicit additional details about the possible causes. The participants' responses to the five whys for the category of "Causes Related to People" were being busy, the lack of education, and being short-staffed were the most frequently cited causes noted by participants in the open-ended comments section. Other notable comments included high patient acuity, lack of support, lack of communication, lack of consistency in practice, short-staffed, low priority of IUC and CAUTI prevention strategies, and physician failure to write catheter discontinue IUC orders. Several participants wrote about forgetting to discontinue the IUC as causes. Respondents noted that at times, the patient's condition, such as being positive for COVID, was an unavoidable UTI cause.

Table 2

Fishbone Causes of CAUTI Related to People

Elements	Respondents (n=50)			
	Related to Nurse Frequency (%)	Related to Physician Frequency (%)	Related to Nursing Assistants Frequency (%)	Not Applicable for any Category Frequency (%)
Perceived Foley as low priority	6 (12%)	11 (22%)	15 (30%)	24 (48%)
Lack of adherence or compliance to policies	5 (12%)	9 (18%)	16 (32%)	27 (54%)
Lack of awareness	4 (8%)	9 (18%)	17 (34%)	22 (44%)
Lack of champion	16 (32%)	18 (36%)	11 (22%)	23 (46%)
Lack of skills competency training	4 (8%)	12 (24%)	17 (34%)	22 (44%)
Lack of support	20 (40%)	10 (20%)	8 (16%)	19 (38%)

Lack of engagement or interaction	7 (14%)	13 (26%)	8 (16%)	25 (50%)
Foley order was not based recommend	5 (10%)	9 (18%)	2 (4%)	35 (70%)
Alternative to Foley was not considered	15 (30%)	14 (28%)	3 (6%)	28 (56%)
Lack of empowerment or initiative	22 (44%)	7 (14%)	2 (4%)	24 (48%)
Forgot to discontinue Foley	15 (30%)	15 (30%)	1 (2%)	25 (50%)
Resistance to change	12 (24%)	9 (18%)	8 (16%)	29 (58%)
Not used smallest size catheter	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

Identified Causes Related to Methods/Processes

Forgetting to discontinue an IUC, not considering alternatives, lack of consistency in implementing IUC practices and CAUTI prevention strategies, and lack of meatal cleaning were the most frequent causes of CAUTI related to methods/processes.

Responses to Open-Ended Five Whys Related to Methods/Processes

Responses to the open-ended questions to the category of causes of CAUTI related to Methods/Processes were like the "Related to People" category, including being busy, high acuity, CAUTI prevention is low priority, shortage of HCP, and lack of support and resources. Other responses from the participants included failure to consider alternatives to IUC, failure of some team members to run a UNIT catheter checklist on every patient with ICU every day, no formal education on the policy regarding Foley versus condom catheter, improper ordering of urine culture, and need for nursing assistants that assist primary nurses in to perform good meatal care.

Table 3*Fishbone Causes of CAUTI Related to Methods/Processes*

Elements	Respondents (n=44)	
	Frequency	%
Forgot to discontinue Foley when no longer necessary	22	(50%)
Alternatives to Foley were not considered	19	(43.18%)
Lack of consistency in the implementation of CAUTI prevention strategies	14	(31.82%)
Lack of meatal cleaning or unable to perform thorough hygiene care	14	(31.82%)
Foley not maintained as a closed system	13	(29.55%)
Urine culture ordered but not indicated	13	(29.55%)
Bladder scanner was not used to verify urinary retention	12	(27.27%)
Improper urine specimen collection practices	11	(25%)
Foley securement device not used	8	(18.18%)
Not Applicable	8	(18.18%)
Lack of performance of hand hygiene	7	(15.91%)
Strict aseptic techniques were not used	6	(13.64%)
Foley bag not below the bladder level	6	(13.64%)
Foley order was not based on recommended indications for use	6	(13.64%)
Policies or protocols not available or up to date	4	(9.09%)
Other (please specify)	0	(0%)

Identified Causes Related to Materials/Equipment

Over 60% of respondents selected "Not Applicable" for the causes of CAUTI related to Materials/Equipment (Table 4). Other participants noted that equipment was not working, that alternatives to Foley catheters and other needed supplies were not available, and the absence of an electronic reminder system were all contributing causes. While "Not Applicable" was selected by most participants, open-ended comments reflected reoccurring themes or consistent responses in the category of causes of CAUTI related to materials/equipment.

Responses to Open-Ended Five Whys Related to Materials/Equipment

In the open-ended question about causes of CAUTI related to materials/equipment, participants noted the lack of a reminder about IUC indication, that alternative supplies to IUC were not appropriate for patients, the presence of defective products, wipes not available, broken bladder scanner, lack of bladder scanner use, and a need for more bladder scanners.

Table 4

Fishbone Causes of CAUTI Related to Materials/Equipment

Elements	Respondents (n=43)	
	Frequency	%
Not Applicable	26	60.47%
Machine or equipment not functioning	9	20.93%
Alternatives to Foley not available (i.e., condom catheter, male or female urinals, Purewick)	6	13.95%
Supplies, materials, or equipment not available (i.e., Foley size, wipes, bladder scanner)	6	13.95%
Lack of electronic health record design. No reminders or alerts.	6	13.95%
Defective or problem with the product or supplies	5	11.63%
Break in the Foley device	0	0%
Other	0	0%

Identified Causes Related to Environment

Twenty-eight of the 42 respondents selected "Not Applicable" for the causes of CAUTI related to the environment. Several respondents selected Poor lighting, bag on the floor, and small space for the sterile field as noteworthy causes of CAUTI related to the Environment (Table 5). Open-ended responses by participants reflect consistency in causes to those in the list of options. The two responses for "other, please specify" were nurses needing more nursing assistant support to perform meatal cleaning and stool.

Responses to Open-Ended Five Whys Related to Environment

Four responses to the Five Whys for causes of CAUTI related to Environment indicated that the overhead light not working, bag above the bladder, and difficulty distinguishing Foley from condom catheter bag from the outside as causes related to the environment.

Table 5

Fishbone Causes of CAUTI Related to Environment

Elements	Respondents (n=42)	
	Frequency	%
Not Applicable	28	66.67%
Poor Lighting	8	19.05%
Bag on the floor when the bed is set to a low position	6	14.29%
Small space-unable to have a sterile field	5	11.9%
Other (please specify)	2	4.76%
Difficult to maneuver with many devices	0	0%
Very warm, too cold, or very humid	0	0%

Identified Causes Related to Other Categories

Respondents were asked to provide information about other perceived categories for causes of CAUTI that were not listed in any other areas of the Fishbone. Twenty of sixty-four participants responded. While many of the comments were restatements of categories listed in the survey, a few noted that patient condition, anatomy, or population group, such as those experiencing homelessness, were perceived causes of CAUTI.

Fishbone Final Comments or Suggestions

Participants were invited to add additional comments or suggestions to improve patient safety and outcomes. Responses specified the need for education and training and need for additional support, availability of perineal care wipes, having a nursing assistant champion,

assigning staff for patients with IUC to follow, providing good hygiene care every 24 hours, and designating one staff person to collect urine specimens to reduce errors in technique.

SWOT Survey

For the SWOT Analysis, closed and open questions were asked from the participants for each category to elicit ideas and insights about practices related to IUC and CAUTI prevention within and outside the units.

Strengths

Participants were given several prompts to respond to the closed-ended question, “What do you think are the strengths related to maintaining a zero CAUTI?” and for open-ended questions was “What do we do well?”. A majority of respondents noted that the strengths were that CAUTI prevention is a priority and adherence or compliance to policies and protocols. Other, often selected strengths were awareness and knowledge of best practices related to IUC and CAUTI prevention practices (i.e., on indications of use and alternatives to Foley), consistency in the implementation of CAUTI prevention strategies (i.e., nurse-driven protocol, huddles, audits), and well-trained or competent individuals in IUC and CAUTI prevention practices (i.e., CAUTI prevention bundles) (see Table 6). Approximately less than half of the participants indicated that leadership support, low staff turnover, the availability of champions, and personnel engagement in prevention activities were strengths.

Table 6*Identified Strengths from the SWOT Survey*

Elements	Respondents (n=57)	
	Frequency	%
Perceived an indwelling urinary catheter and CAUTI prevention as a priority	45	79%
Adherence or compliance to policies and or protocol based on best practices	42	74%
Awareness and knowledge of best practices related to indwelling urinary catheter and CAUTI prevention practices	37	65%
(i.e., on indications of use and alternatives to Foley)	36	63%
Consistency in implementation of CAUTI prevention strategies (i.e., nurse-driven protocol, huddles, audits)		
Well trained or competent in IUC and CAUTI prevention practices	34	60%
Leadership support	31	54%
No staffing shortage or low turnover	31	54%
Availability of champions (i.e., nurse, physician, or nursing assistants)	29	51%
Engagement (interaction) of healthcare personnel (nurse-physician-nursing assistant)	29	51%
Other	1	2%
Consistency in implementation of (i.e., nurse-driven protocol, huddles, audits) or documentation	0	0%
No resistance to change among healthcare personnel	0	0%

Weaknesses

The participants were given prompts for closed-ended questions of “What do you think are the weaknesses related to having CAUTI events?” The open-ended question, “What do we need to improve?” was asked of participants to elicit information about perceived weaknesses in CAUTI prevention. The main weakness identified by almost 60% of respondents is high turnover or staff shortage. Areas of weakness that 36-39% of respondents noted included a lack of consistency in implementing CAUTI prevention strategies, lack of adherence or compliance to policies and or protocol based on best practices, and the absence of available champions availability. Few participants (20-30%) indicated that perceived IUC and CAUT prevention were

a low priority, lack of awareness and knowledge of best practices related to IUC and CAUTI prevention practices, lack of engagement in prevention activities, missing leadership support, and a lack of training on IUC and CAUTI prevention practices.

Respondents were asked to provide answers to the open-ended question about weaknesses. Some of the comments provided included the high turnover, lack of support and assistance from nursing assistants for ADLs, lack of ancillary support, pandemic, and patients with a catheter can have UTI, CAUTI not due to the catheter, stress, and antibiotics.

Table 7

Identified Weaknesses from the SWOT Survey

Elements	Respondents (n=56)	
	Frequency	%
High turnover or staffing shortage	33	59%
Lack of consistency in the implementation of CAUTI prevention strategies (i.e., nurse-driven protocol, huddles, audits)	22	39%
Lack of adherence or compliance to policies and or protocol based on best practices	20	36%
Lack of availability of champions (i.e., nurse, physician, or nursing assistants)	20	36%
Perceived IUC and CAUTI prevention as a low priority	17	30%
Lack of awareness and knowledge of best practices related to indwelling urinary catheter and CAUTI prevention practices	16	29%
Lack of engagement (interaction) of healthcare personnel (nurse-physician-nursing assistant)	14	25%
Lack of leadership support	11	20%
Lack of training	11	20%
Resistance to change among healthcare personnel	0	0%
Other	5	9%

Note: Participants' responses from two MICUs

Opportunities

The question, “What are some opportunities related to IUC and CAUTI prevention practices?” was given several prompts to respond to the closed-ended question. The open-ended question, “What can we do that is not being done?” asked to elicit information from participants about how practice can be improved. Participants were given several prompts to respond to the questions. The majority of the participants noted that the opportunities were improved staffing by having additional help, enhanced or improved healthcare personnel knowledge and or skills, improved communication and engagement among HCP, availability of resources (i.e., materials, literature, or educator on best practices and improved patient satisfaction, patient safety and outcomes, cooperation of patients' family, and administrative support (Table 8).

Table 8

Identified Opportunities from the SWOT Survey

Elements	Respondents (n=56)	
	Frequency	%
High turnover or short staffing	33	59%
Perceived an indwelling urinary catheter and CAUTI prevention as a priority	17	30%
Lack of Adherence or compliance to policies and or protocol based on best practices	20	36%
Lack of availability of champions (i.e., nurse, physician, or nursing assistants)	20	36%
Lack of awareness and knowledge of best practices related to indwelling urinary catheter and CAUTI prevention practices	16	29%
Lack of consistency in implementation of (i.e., nurse-driven protocol, huddles, audits) or documentation	22	39%
Lack of engagement (interaction) of healthcare personnel (nurse-physician-nursing assistant)	14	25%
Lack of leadership support	11	20%
Lack of training	11	20%
Resistance to change among healthcare personnel	0	0%
Other	5	9%

Note: Participants' responses from two MICUs

Threats

Participants were given several prompts to respond to the questions, “What are some threats to IUC and CAUTI prevention practices?” for the closed-ended question. The open-ended question, “What obstacles are in the way of our CAUTI prevention efforts?” were asked to elicit responses related to perceived barriers to CAUTI prevention activities. The threats (n=54) identified by the participants were the following: lack of time or time constraints, high acuity patients transferred from other departments, fear of negative attitude or retaliation, lack of compliance by other department healthcare personnel, and lack of support from other disciplines or department, resistance to change of other department HCP, patients will choose other healthcare facilities with low organization public ratings, and leadership changes (Figure 9). High acuity, lack of time, fear of negative attitude, and lack of compliance were the threats identified by each MICUs and as a combined unit.

Table 9

Identified Threats from the SWOT Survey

Elements	Respondents (n=56)	
	Frequency	%
Changes in leadership	3	5%
Fear of negative attitude or retaliation	18	32%
High acuity patients transferred from other departments	28	53%
Lack of compliance by other department healthcare personnel	18	42%
Lack of support from other disciplines or department	15	26%
Lack of time or time constraints	29	68%
Low organization public ratings (i.e., CMS)	5	11%
Patients will choose other healthcare facilities	8	32%
Resistance to change of other department healthcare personnel	11	26%
Other (please specify)	2	5%

Note: Participants' responses from two MICUs

Comments or Suggestions Category

Participants were asked to provide comments about Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats not addressed in the SWOT survey. They were also asked to provide recommendations for practice improvement. Each category had similar themes, such as training and education, supplies and equipment, teams, and processes and tools. Participants' suggestions included the need for more resources, specifically staffing, equipment, training, hands-on support by nursing assistants, rounds, checklist, and need for champions.

TAP Survey

The TAP is a gap analysis tool to identify awareness and perception of HCP related to IUC and CAUTI prevention practices. The TAP survey results showed the leading and lagging elements of IUC and CAUTI prevention practices among HCP in both MICUs (Table 10). The leading elements were senior and unit level leadership, a pre-connected, sealed catheter system and maintaining a urinary system closed, identifying patients with IUC, and reviewing the daily needs of IUC. Lagging responses were no two-person for IUC insertion and physician champion, and lack of alerts or reminders to discontinue IUC. Lagging related to IUC and CAUTI prevention practices in the PACU and ED needs to be explored to understand the participants' perceptions better.

Table 10*TAP Survey Results*

Domain	Leading/Facilitators	Lagging/Barriers
I. General Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Senior and unit-level leadership involvement • Training provided to all HCP (given the responsibility to insert, assist with insertion, or maintain IUC) of aseptic techniques, proper urinary care maintenance procedures, proper placement of the drainage bag, and use of bladder scanners • Routinely audits (monitor and document) adherence of HCP to IUC indication appropriateness, aseptic technique for IUC, proper maintenance procedures • Routinely provide feedback to all HCP on adherence to appropriate indications, proper aseptic technique, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physician champions
II. Appropriate Indications for IUC Insertion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ordering providers use IUC for appropriate indications • Use of alternative strategies • Use of bladder scanner 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Order provided in ED before insertion of IUC • Ordering of IUC for appropriate indications by ED providers • Documentation of an indication when ED physicians order IUC
III. Aseptic IUC Insertion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of supplies/kits for proper aseptic insertion of IUC • Documentation of insertion procedure by person inserting IUC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement of two-person to be present for IUC insertion

IV. Proper Indwelling Urinary Catheter Maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of preconnected, sealed urinary catheter drainage systems • Personnel keep the urinary drainage system closed to maintain sterility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the ED, pre-connected, sealed urinary drainage systems with urine meters used in critically ill patients to avoid breaking the system once transferred to ICU
V. Timely Removal of IUC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of patients with urinary catheters in place • Daily review of patients with urinary catheters for continued need 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IUC removal if no indication for continued use after surgery in PACU • Facility use alert or reminders, or stop orders for IUC removal • Physicians respond to reminders by removing unnecessary IUC
VI. Appropriate Urine Culturing Practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport of urine specimen immediately to the lab 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None

Discussion

The purpose of this project was to determine the gaps between published evidence-based guidelines and current IUC and CAUTI prevention practices in two MICUs where CAUTIs remain high. The objectives were to identify causes of CAUTI, determine strengths, weaknesses, threats, and opportunities, and understand the level of awareness and perceptions of HCP. The gap analysis helped identify elements that facilitated and impeded IUC and CAUTI prevention implementation strategies (Snyder et al., 2021; White et al., 2020). The simultaneous use of diverse assessments helped identify target areas for improvement activities.

Fishbone Causes of CAUTI

The process for conducting a Fishbone analysis is based on brainstorming. In brainstorming, participants contribute ideas spontaneously to solve problems or determine causes. As a group, participants hear each other's responses, which triggers further thinking and responding, eventually leading to a winnowing down of potential causes into a few agreed-upon concepts. Unfortunately, due to the COVID-19 social distancing restrictions, the Fishbone brainstorming technique could not be used as intended. Instead, this activity was converted into a survey format with opportunities for open-ended responses from participants. Survey response options were developed by the primary investigator based on a review of the literature for causes of CAUTI. The format did not allow participants to share responses and build upon the brainstorming, re-examining, or narrowing the potential causes. While the process was not as dynamic or organic as it would have been if conducted as designed, and a clear root cause for CAUTI was not determined, it was not without valuable results.

The most frequent response for each of the categories on the survey was 'Not Applicable.' There were two areas of exception, including 20 responses for 'Lack of Support'

in the causes related to the People/Nurses category, versus 19 for 'Not Applicable.' In the causes related to the Methods/Processes category, 50% of participants selected "Forgot to discontinue Foley" and 43% selected "Alternatives to Foley were not considered." Forgetting to discontinue the Foley was also noted by 30% of respondents as one of the causes of People/Nurses and People/Physicians. Approximately the same number of participants noted that not considering alternatives to a Foley were possible causes related to People/Nurses and People/Physicians.

Across the causes related to people category, participants indicated that there was a "Lack of champion," a commonly identified barrier in the absence of one who can assist in implementing CAUTI prevention strategies (Fletcher et al., 2016; Lo et al., 2014; Saint et al., 2013; Saint et al., 2014). Often, HCP perceive that CAUTI is not a priority and that not having an IUC increases workload (Gyesi-Appiah et al., 2020; Krein et al., 2013; Meddings et al., 2014). Without a champion, there is a potential for HCP to continue to be unwilling to support or participate in CAUTI prevention activities (Harrod et al., 2013; Lo et al., 2014). A champion can help overcome the resistance to change by other HCP (Fakih et al., 2014; Samparatkumar et al., 2016).

Other notable findings include the 44% of respondents who indicated "Lack of empowerment" and the 40% who noted "Lack of support" in causes related to People/Nurses. The lack of empowerment of nurses may be related to the inconsistent application of the nurse-driven protocol to remove IUC. The nurse-driven protocol, where the removal of an IUC is initiated based on assessment and nursing scope of practice, based on facility policy and procedure, without a provider order. Reasons nurses do not consistently apply this intervention are several, including that they may not agree with the protocol, they are not comfortable removing an IUC independently without a physician's order, they are reluctant to address the

patient's incontinence care without an IUC in place, or they are not confident in speaking with physicians about removing an IUC. Lack of application of the nurse-driven protocol contributes to prolonged IUC use, increasing CAUTI risk (Lo et al., 2014; Meddings et al., 2014; Saint et al., 2014). Empowering nurses to apply the nurse-driven protocol, with proper training and support by organization leadership and physicians, can reduce the risk of CAUTI (Meddings et al., 2014).

The Fishbone activity highlighted areas of weaknesses in patient care that could be solved quickly. Twenty-one percent of participants noted in the causes related to the Equipment/Supplies category that the bladder scanner was not functional, and 14% indicated that alternatives to IUC (e.g., condom catheters) were not available. Other supplies necessary for patient care and IUC management (e.g., wipes) were not available, and that there is a lack of chart alerts. Finally, 19% of participants indicated that overhead lighting was not functional in the causes related to the environment category and the Foley bag was on the floor. Many of these findings could be identified and acted on by having a monthly supply and equipment checklist audit.

The Fishbone survey allowed respondents to add open-ended comments about the contributing causes of CAUTI. Many noted a heavy workload, short staffing, and high acuity as additional causes. While the Fishbone activity did not determine a specific cause for CAUTI, the survey demonstrated that respondents perceive that the causes discussed in published articles also contribute to CAUTI. When safe to do so, an in-person Fishbone activity should be conducted, and the results compared to these, to determine the facility-specific root causes.

SWOT Improvement Strategies

A SWOT analysis can help in developing strategies for improvement in an organization. Like the Fishbone, a SWOT analysis is a brainstorming activity where participants gather to spontaneously generate ideas in each of the four categories, strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. Ideas are discussed, ranked and then winnowed into a few agreed upon by the group as most important or meaningful. Due to the COVID-19 social distancing restrictions, the SWOT activity was converted to a survey format. Participants were able to select from responses developed by the author based on a review of the literature for common themes related to organizational strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. Participants were allowed to offer additional open-ended comments to describe their thoughts around each of the categories. Because this was not a true brainstorming activity, where participants could spontaneously develop ideas, discuss, and further refine their responses; the findings may not necessarily reflect ideas that might have been generated otherwise.

The strengths that many participants perceived related to CAUTI prevention can be used to build upon as these are signs of readiness for making change possible (Samparthkumar et al., 2016). Despite there being continued CAUTI events, respondents feel that prevention is a priority, that they do adhere to policies and are aware of best practices that they consistently implement, and that they are well-trained. However, perceived strengths can potentially be a barrier if participants do not feel that they need more training or better awareness. More information is needed to determine level of competence in practice, understanding of policies, and readiness to learn.

In large numbers, respondents perceive that there is great opportunity for change and improvement in CAUTI prevention with appropriate staffing. This recurrent focus on staffing

and workload issues provides leaders with insight into how the work environment is perceived. To ensure success in implementing CAUTI prevention practices, healthcare organizations must establish goals and priorities and allocate resources appropriately, including appropriate staffing of personnel to perform their responsibilities of quality care (Samparathkumar et al., 2016). In problematic staffing situations, patient care can be compromised, leading to adverse outcomes. Interestingly, though participants felt they were well-trained, they also reflected that enhanced knowledge was an opportunity for improved practice. This is especially important as many respondents reflected that lack of consistency and adherence were weaknesses that the organization faces.

Participants indicated that high turnover, lack of consistency, lack of adherence to policies, and the lack of champions were essential challenges. A perceived increase in workload due to high staff turnover and competing priorities with IUC practices and a lack of adherence to policies due to outdated training and the use of traditional practices can all impede prevention efforts (Harrod et al., 2013; Krein et al., 2013; Lo et al., 2014; Meddings et al., 2014). Policies and protocols can help provide guidance, address the importance of compliance and adherence, standardize the implementation of interventions, and increase accountability (Fakih et al., 2014). With policies in place, HCP will be aware of their responsibilities, such as use of aseptic technique for IUC insertion and the use of bundled strategies, which can help guide practice, (AHRQ, n.d.; CDC, n.d.; Lo et al., 2014; Meddings et al., 2014). As in the Fishbone survey, the lack of champions, was identified as a weakness. A trained HCP champion can help facilitate the roll-out of the strategies at the unit level to support those who may be resistant to change or revert to traditional practice (Fakih et al., 2014; Lo et al., 2014).

The lack of time and high acuity are identified threats that have the potential to harm or damage CAUTI prevention efforts. Being able to anticipate threats and take precautions can help the organization minimize the negative impacts of these factors. Acting on the opportunities for success, namely improving staffing, can potentially offset the recognized threats.

The findings from SWOT analysis helped identify what respondents think the organization is doing well, where there are opportunities for improvement, and areas of weakness and threats to functioning or improvement. The information is helpful in planning strategies for improvement in CAUTI prevention. Conducting an in-person SWOT analysis that includes further examining internal weaknesses versus external threats should be conducted to assure that the organization understands any additional factors not identified in the modified survey format.

TAP Awareness, Knowledge, and Perceptions of Infection Prevention Practices

The TAP survey showed that most of the elements from CDC guideline recommendations have been at least partially implemented. This is not a surprise since the issue of inconsistency in implementation of CAUTI prevention strategies has been identified as an organizational challenge. The results for this survey were calculated using a CDC-designed scoring system, where a pre-determined measure indicates whether an item is a leading or lagging indicator. The CDC calculations identified only a few things that were considered lagging.

Leading indicators are proactive elements that facilitate prevention practices. Respondents identified many leading indicators, such as senior and unit level leadership involvement, routine audits and feedback, use of alternative strategies of IUC, and use of bladder scanner. Other leading indicators were perceived competency assessment received upon hire and

annually, use of pre-connected sealed IUC, maintained a closed system, and urine specimen sent to the laboratory immediately after collection.

On the other hand, respondents perceived few lagging indicators, which are elements that impede CAUTI prevention efforts. In line with the Fishbone and SWOT survey findings, a notable lagging indicator was the lack of physician champion. Additionally, two-person IUC insertion, the lack of organization-wide technological alerts for IUC removal, and physicians-specific reminders for removal were identified as lagging elements. These results correspond with the perceived causes of CAUTI due to forgetting to discontinue the IUC and the lack of alerts from the Fishbone and SWOT surveys. These are clear areas where the organization can target for improvement.

Several of the lagging indicators were actions that take place in other departments, such as the ED and PACU. Because MICU participants responded 'Unknown' to these items, they were flagged as lagging. The survey should be completed in those units or facility-wide to understand whether those unit-specific items are truly lagging indicators. A facility-wide survey would also be helpful in better understanding those items that were not found to be either leading or lagging but which could be targeted for practice improvement.

Key Recommendations for Prevention Program Improvement

Besides adopting EBP and implementing best practice recommendations, multiple strategies implemented simultaneously are commonly used to prevent CAUTI (Meddings et al., 2014). Consistent with several studies, the project's findings support that healthcare systems widely used a combination of strategies, appeared to be more effective and that there is no single strategy to reduce CAUTI (Jordan et al., 2017; Lo et al., 2014; Meddings et al., 2014 Purvis et al., 2017; Theobald et al., 2017). Key findings from the three surveys helped determine priority

areas for improvement in CAUTI prevention, which focus on strengthening and supporting practices to enhance patient care outcomes.

Physician Champion

The result of the project supports the need for a CAUTI prevention champion who will speak up for the protocols and practices and share their knowledge and skills with others (Fakih et al., 2014; Lo et al., 2014). A champion may provide technical assistance related to IUC practices, such as answers questions and feedback during observation of skills performed by others (Fakih et al., 2014; Richards et al., 2017). By having an identified champion, the initiative is kept at the unit level, which can help with relationship building and trust, leading to better buy-in (Krein et al., 2013; Lo et al., 2013). Empowered champions, who are perceived to be closer to the clinical care teams, help create awareness to change the culture to improve patient outcomes (Fakih et al., 2014; Gyesi-Appiah et al., 2020).

Defining the role, recruiting, and training nurse and physician champions is essential to ensure commitment and help increase awareness and educate other HCP (Fakih et al., 2014; Fletcher et al., 2016; Gyesi-Appiah et al., 2020). Having a physician as champion has the added benefit of being able to write an order for IUC removal when no longer necessary, which can impact the issues of forgetting to discontinue an IUC or considering alternatives, both issues noted in this project's findings (Fakih et al., 2014; Fletcher et al., 2016; Lo et al., 2014).

Two-Person IUC Insertion Protocol

Findings supported the need to update policies to include a two-person IUC insertion protocol, which is a recommendation of both the CDC and other organizations (Belizario, 2015; Fletcher-Gutowski, 2019; Galiczewski & Shurpin, 2017).

Having designated HCP and a two-person team for IUC insertion can significantly reduce CAUTI events (CDC HICPAC, 2019; Fletcher-Gutowski & Cecil, 2019; Galiczewski & Shurpin, 2017; Lo et al., 2014; Meddings et al., 2014; Yokoe et al., 2014). In one study in an ICU, a trained HCP observed and used a checklist to verify sterile technique of fellow staff performing an IUC insertion, resulting in a CAUTI rate reduction from 2.24 to 0 per 1000 catheter days (Galiczewski & Shurpin, 2017; Fletcher-Gutowski & Cecil, 2019). In this scenario, the procedure is halted when the insertion technique is compromised (Fletcher-Gutowski & Cecil, 2019). Besides reducing CAUTI rates, the two-person ICU insertion with a checklist helps lower the incidence of contamination, increases awareness of adherence to best practice and patient safety, and reduced costs (Fletcher-Gutowski & Cecil, 2019). With adherence to the EBP guidelines reflected in policy and protocol, CAUTI events can be reduced significantly (Marra et al., 2011; Metrayonis & Gargan, 2019).

Removal Alerts

The development of standardized alerts or reminders, particularly to discontinue the IUC and reduce prolonged insertion duration is critical. Prompt removal of the IUC is essential in reducing CAUTI (CDC, 2019; Clayton, 2017; Lo et al., 2014; Meddings et al., 2014; Tyson et al., 2018). As reflected in this project's findings, providers often forget to discontinue IUCs, which causes extended periods of insertion, exposing patients to greater CAUTI risk. Checklists or reminders, whether written, verbal, or electronic, can be beneficial not only in a complex MICU setting, but also facility-wide (Gupta et al., 2017; Meddings et al., 2014). Checklists or reminders for indication, maintenance and care, and prompt removal should be integrated into patient care processes (Clayton, 2017; Meddings et al., 2014; Theobald et al., 2017). Because reminders can be ignored, implementing an automated system to discontinue or renew the IUC

order should be integrated into the EHR (Clayton, 2017; Meddings et al., 2014). In one study, a criteria-based reminder for IUC use contributed to a reduction in the number of CAUTI events as it helped guide healthcare professionals in assessing the necessity of an IUC (Chen et al., 2013; Clayton, 2017). Reminders or checklists as CPG implementation strategies are vital to continue their influence on the successful adoption of EBPs (Conner et al., 2013; Jordan et al., 2017).

Staffing

HCP participants reflected a perception of inadequate staffing, lack of time, and high patient acuity as reasons for not performing or adhering to prevention practices. With appropriate staffing, HCP can feel better prepared to take the time necessary to perform a two-person IUC insertion and provide the maintenance and care required. Staffing that allows for the development of a designated CAUTI team that includes HCP and support staff involved in patient care, who can assist with patients' toileting activities, can reduce this burden from nurses, allowing more time for proper insertion and attention to documentation (Krein et al., 2013). Specialty staff, such as wound ostomy and incontinence nurses, advanced care nurse practitioners, and others can also be enlisted to participate in IUC care and monitoring to contribute to improving patient outcomes, cost, and length of stay reductions, and sustained prevention practices (Ballard et al., 2018; Carr et al., 2017; Greene, 2020; Panchisin, 2017; Park et al., 2018).

Education

Education is vital to increase awareness of the best practices to eliminate gaps in knowledge by the HCP involved in IUC care. Standardized and routine education for the HCP who have patients with IUC is critical. At a minimum, annual education and competency assessment can ensure EBP uptake and standardization and reduce patient harm (Fink et al.,

2012). In one of study, a facility-wide education program helped reduced CAUTI as HCP gained knowledge (Conner et al., 2013; Welden, 2013). Similarly, multiple strategies, such as circulating continuous information, providing formal and informal teaching sessions, and observational audits, can led to increased knowledge, awareness, and ownership among health professionals (Gyesi-Appiah, Brown, & Clifton, 2020). Health professionals need to be made aware of and have their knowledges evaluated on EBP guidelines and be trained and return demonstration on prevention practice strategies to achieve optimal outcomes (Fink et al., 2012; Gyesi-Appiah, Brown, & Clifton, 2020).

Evaluation

The CDC TAP survey is a promising standardized gap analysis tool that should be conducted facility-wide to better understand the strategies implemented in all areas of the facility in order to target and strengthen unit-based and organizational CAUTI prevention strategies. (Snyder et al., 2021). After change in practice is implemented, a follow-up of the TAP survey in three and six months can help determine if any improvement has occurred.

Any evaluation should be embraced by all HCP to achieve facility-wide change. Engagement of HCP and leadership involvement is vital to transforming evidence into the practice setting. The importance of multidisciplinary team engagement with the common goal of patient safety creates a culture of safety based on evidence that has already been proven to be effective (Quinn, 2015; Scanlon et al., 2017). With engagement, HCWs are accountable for their actions, leading to more awareness of EBP to make better patient decisions and care (Underwood, 2015).

Concerted efforts, buy-in, and support from HCWs and leadership at all levels are necessary for the successful implementation of any EBP initiative with a culture of safety as the

center of focus Purvis et al., 2017; Shea et al., 2019). Efforts to prevent CAUTI must be enhanced and measured to determine if change for improvement occurred with the update of EBP initiatives; the sustainability of CAUTI prevention strategies is crucial to delivering service, a high quality of care (Quinn, 2015; Scanlon et al., 2017). Future studies are necessary to increase understanding of perceptions and awareness among leadership, nursing management, nursing assistants, and physician's reduction CAUTI events, specifically in the ICU setting.

Limitations

Given the sample size for each survey and the uniqueness of the two MICU as the designated COVID cohort units, findings may not be generalizable to other patient populations and clinical settings. Due to the pandemic surge, Fishbone and SWOT data may be skewed as in-person brainstorming was not conducted due to the social distancing restrictions. The additional circumstances of the MICUs designated as cohort COVID units, high acuity, short staffing, and impending lack of supplies and equipment may have been influenced the perceptions of HCP in completing the surveys.

Conclusion

The use of assessment tools designed to look at root causes, business planning strategies, and gaps in infection prevention practices provides an in-depth understanding of the current state of CAUTI prevention activities in the MICU. The project findings demonstrated no single element that directly causes CAUTI, and that no one strategy can reduce CAUTIs. The presence of such a wide variety of factors contributing to CAUTI demonstrates that a multi-pronged prevention strategy will be most effective (Lo et al., 2014; Meddings et al., Metroyanis & Gargan, 2019; Purvis et al., 2017; Shea et al., 2018).

Healthcare organizations can decrease barriers to CAUTI prevention practices by gathering baseline data related to gaps, weaknesses, threats and by examining strengths and opportunities from the HCP perspective. As healthcare organizations continually strive for excellence, they must identify organizational priorities to allocate resources appropriately, such as having adequate staffing, available supplies and working equipment, a robust electronic health record system, and policies and procedures that provide guidance.

Adopting EBP guidelines and assuring their implementation through policies and procedures, algorithms, checklists, and reminders are essential to ensure high-quality care practices. Equally essential is the need for continuous monitoring of quality improvement metrics, including audits of compliance and data feedback to the stakeholders to ensure adherence to EBP guidelines.

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APPENDIX A

Fishbone Survey Informed Consent

California State University, Fullerton Research Study Consent Form

Study Title: Decreasing Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections (CAUTIs)
Protocol Number: HSR-20-21-155
Researcher: Luisa Chong, California State University Fullerton student

I am Luisa Chong, representing California State University Fullerton as a Doctorate of Nursing Practice student. I am the Primary Investigator conducting this research study that is a quality improvement project under the advisement of Dr. Rachel McClanahan. You are being asked to take part in a quality improvement activity that is carried out by me. This consent form explains the quality improvement project and your part when you join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. You can ask me as the primary investigator to explain anything you do not understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide not to participate in the study.

What is this study about?

The purpose of the quality improvement is to determine the gaps between the published evidence-based practice guidelines and current clinical practice related to indwelling urinary catheter and catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTI) prevention. The objective of the quality improvement activity Fishbone is to identify the underlying (root) causes of catheter-associated urinary tract infections.

You are being asked to participate in the quality improvement activity as healthcare personnel working in the Medical Intensive Care unit who are familiar with the policies and standard of practice. Your participation will provide insights and ideas related to indwelling urinary catheter practices and CAUTI prevention to understand better and tailor specific interventions to improve patient outcomes. You cannot participate in this study if you are a nurse, nursing assistant, and physicians at all levels who do not work in the Medical Intensive Care Unit due to a lack of familiarity with the protocol and standard of care.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you participate in activity, you will be asked to respond to the questions. The participant may refuse to answer any question in a questionnaire. An email with the Informed Consent information to participate and instructions will be provided with a link to the survey through Survey Monkey. If the participants click to *disagree*, they will not be able to view the survey, however, if they click *agree*, they will be able to view the survey and answer the questions, which will serve as consent to participate in completing the survey. At the beginning of the survey, participants will be asked to complete a Professional Demographic Survey.

Professional Demographic Survey: Questions are regarding the participants' current work area/unit name, work shift, current position, role, or profession, length of time in the current role,

position, or profession, and length of time working in the current work area/unit, educational level, age, and gender. Demographic data will be collected to help identify the unique characteristics of healthcare personnel who are participating in the activity for each unit.

Fishbone: A quality improvement tool to identify the root causes of CAUTIs.
Online What are the causes of CAUTIs? The question of why is asked four
(Survey Monkey) more times to determine the root causes.
 The estimated time it will take is 5 to 15 minutes.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

Participants often feel the direct benefit from feeling that they have helped improve patient care by participating in the activity. Benefits include participants have contributions to improve patient outcomes by providing insights and sharing ideas related to the practices of assessment, maintenance, and removal of indwelling urinary catheter and CAUTI prevention. As a participant, you may become more aware of your perceptions, knowledge, and attitude towards indwelling urinary catheter practices and CAUTI prevention.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

The quality improvement activity Fishbone does not contain foreseeable or potential risks. There are no potential risks from taking part in this study. You may choose not to answer the question that makes you uncomfortable.

Will my information be kept confidential?

The data for this study will be kept confidential to the extent allowed by law. No published results will identify you, and your name will not be associated with the findings. The Fishbone Survey, which is completed through Survey Monkey, is a secured link and will not be linked to the participants' names. The researcher, Luisa Chong, will have access to the data.

The study results may be published or presented at professional meetings, but all research participants' identities will remain confidential. The data will be kept for a minimum of 3 years after completing the study as required by California State University Fullerton.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study? No

There will be no costs to you for taking part in this study. You will not receive money or any other form of compensation for taking part in this quality improvement project. Upon completing an activity, participant's seven-digit number will be placed in a random drawing for one of four \$25 Amazon gift cards.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher Luisa Chong at (323) 409-6643 or lchong@dhs.lacounty.gov.

If you have questions about your rights as a quality improvement participant or would like to report a concern or complaint about the quality improvement activity, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719 or email irb@fullerton.edu.

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this quality improvement project is entirely voluntary. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and or I understand the terms used in this consent form. By clicking agree, I *agree* that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this study.

APPENDIX B

SWOT Analysis Survey Informed Consent

California State University, Fullerton Research Study Consent Form

Study Title: Decreasing Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections (CAUTIs)
Protocol Number: HSR-20-21-155
Researcher: Luisa Chong, California State University Fullerton student

I am Luisa Chong, representing California State University Fullerton as a Doctorate of Nursing Practice student. I am the Primary Investigator conducting this research study that is a quality improvement project under the advisement of Dr. Rachel McClanahan. You are being asked to take part in a quality improvement activity that is carried out by me. This consent form explains the quality improvement project and your part when you join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. You can ask me as the primary investigator to explain anything you do not understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide not to participate in the study.

What is this study about?

The purpose of the quality improvement is to determine the gaps between the published evidence-based practice guidelines and current clinical practice related to indwelling urinary catheter and catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTI) prevention. The objective of the quality improvement activity Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) Analysis survey is to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to practices of indwelling urinary catheter (IUC) assessment, management, and removal related to indwelling urinary catheter practices and CAUTI prevention.

You are being asked to participate in the quality improvement activity as healthcare personnel working in the Medical Intensive Care unit who is familiar with the policies and standard of practice. Your participation will provide insights and ideas related to indwelling urinary catheter practices and CAUTI prevention to understand better and tailor specific interventions to improve patient outcomes. You cannot participate in this study if you are a nurse, nursing assistant, and physicians at all levels who do not work in the Medical Intensive Care Unit due to a lack of familiarity with the protocol and standard of care.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you participate in activity, you will be asked to respond to the questions. The participant may refuse to answer any question in a questionnaire.

An email with the Informed Consent information to participate and instructions will be provided with a link to the survey through Survey Monkey. If the participants click to *disagree*, they will not be able to view the survey, however, if they click *agree*, they will be able to view the survey and answer the questions, which will serve as consent to participate in completing the survey. At

the beginning of the survey, participants will be asked to complete a Professional Demographic Survey.

Professional Demographic Survey: Questions are regarding the participants' current work area/unit name, work shift, current position, role, or professional level, number of years/months in the current role, position, or profession, and number of years/months working in the current work area/unit, educational level, age, and gender. Demographic data will be collected to help identify the unique characteristics of healthcare personnel who are participating in the activity for each unit.

SWOT Analysis: A strategic planning tool to identify the strengths, weakness, opportunities, and threats related to practices of IUC assessment and management and CAUTI prevention. 1) What do you think are the strengths related to maintaining a zero CAUTI? What do we do well? 2) What do you think are the weaknesses related to having CAUTI events? What do we need to improve? 3) What are some opportunities related to CAUTI event? What can we do that is not being done? 4) What are some threats to prevent CAUTI? What obstacles are in the way of our CAUTI prevention efforts?
 Online
 (Survey Monkey)
 The estimated time it will take is 5 to 15 minutes.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

Participants often feel the direct benefit from feeling that they have helped improve patient care by participating in the activity. Benefits include participants have contributions to improve patient outcomes by providing insights and sharing ideas related to the practices of assessment, maintenance, and removal of indwelling urinary catheter and CAUTI prevention. As a participant, you may become more aware of your perceptions, knowledge, and attitude towards indwelling urinary catheter practices and CAUTI prevention.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

The quality improvement activity does not contain foreseeable or potential risks. There are no potential risks from taking part in this study. You may choose not to answer the question that makes you uncomfortable.

Will my information be kept confidential?

The data for this study will be kept confidential to the extent allowed by law. No published results will identify you, and your name will not be associated with the findings. The SWOT Analysis Survey, which is completed through Survey Monkey, is a secured link and will not be linked to the participants' names. The researcher, Luisa Chong, will have access to the data. The study results may be published or presented at professional meetings, but all research participants' identities will remain confidential. The data will be kept for a minimum of 3 years after completing the study as required by California State University Fullerton.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study? No

There will be no costs to you for taking part in this study. You will not receive money or any other form of compensation for taking part in this quality improvement project. Upon completing

an activity, participant's seven-digit number will be placed in a random drawing for one of four \$25 Amazon gift cards.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher Luisa Chong at (323) 409-6643 or lchong@dhs.lacounty.gov.

If you have questions about your rights as a quality improvement participant or would like to report a concern or complaint about the quality improvement activity, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719 or email irb@fullerton.edu.

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this quality improvement project is entirely voluntary. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and or I understand the terms used in this consent form. By clicking on *agree*, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this study.

APPENDIX C

TAP Survey Informed Consent

California State University, Fullerton Research Study Consent Form

Study Title: Decreasing Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections (CAUTIs)
Protocol Number: HSR-20-21-155
Researcher: Luisa Chong, California State University Fullerton student

I am Luisa Chong, representing California State University Fullerton (CSUF) as a Doctorate of Nursing Practice student. I am the Primary Investigator conducting this research study that is a quality improvement project under the advisement of Dr. Rachel McClanahan. You are being asked to take part in a quality improvement activity that is carried out by me. This consent form explains the quality improvement project and your part when you join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. You can ask me as the primary investigator to explain anything you do not understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide not to participate in the study.

What is this study about?

The purpose of the quality improvement is to determine the gaps between the published evidence-based practice guidelines and current clinical practice related to indwelling urinary catheter and catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTI) prevention. The objective of the quality improvement activity TAP survey is to identify the level of awareness, perceptions, and knowledge among healthcare personnel related to indwelling urinary catheter practices and CAUTI prevention strategies. You are being asked to participate in the quality improvement activity as healthcare personnel working in the Medical Intensive Care unit who is familiar with the policies and standard of practice. Your participation will provide insights and ideas related to indwelling urinary catheter practices and CAUTI prevention to understand better and tailor specific interventions to improve patient outcomes. You cannot participate in this study if you are a nurse, nursing assistant, and physicians at all levels who do not work in the Medical Intensive Care Unit due to a lack of familiarity with the protocol and standard of care.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you participate in activity, you will be asked to respond to the questions. The participant may refuse to answer any question in a questionnaire. An email with the Informed Consent information to participate and instructions will be provided with a link to the survey through Survey Monkey. If the participants click to *disagree*, they will not be able to view the survey, however, if they click *agree*, they will be able to view the survey and answer the questions, which will serve as consent to participate in completing the survey. At the beginning of the survey, participants will be asked to complete a Professional Demographic Survey.

Professional Demographic Survey: Questions are regarding the participants' current work area/unit name, work shift, current position, role, or profession, length of time in the current role, position, or profession, and length of time working in the current work area/unit, educational

level, age, and gender. Demographic data will be collected to help identify the unique characteristics of healthcare personnel who are participating in the activity for each unit.

TAP survey: An infection prevention and gap analysis tool developed by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) to identify the level of awareness, knowledge, and perceptions among healthcare workers related to practices of IUC assessment and management and CAUTI prevention. The TAP tool has 49 questions, which are divided into six sections: I. General Infrastructure, II. Appropriate Indications for Insertions, III. Aseptic Insertion, IV. Proper Catheter Maintenance, V. Timely Removal, and VI. Appropriate Urine Culturing Practices. Each item requires a Yes, No, or Unknown response in section I. In sections II through VI, a six-point Likert scale that requires a response from 1, which is Never, to 6, which is Unknown (CDC, 2016). Each section also has a comment area for participants to provide additional information. The estimated time it will take is 5 to 10 minutes.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

Participants often feel the direct benefit from feeling that they have helped improve patient care by participating in the activity. Benefits include participants have contributions to improve patient outcomes by providing their insights and sharing ideas related to the practices of assessment, maintenance, and removal of indwelling urinary catheter and CAUTI prevention. As a participant, you may become more aware of your perceptions, knowledge, and attitude towards indwelling urinary catheter practices and CAUTI prevention.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

The quality improvement activity TAP survey does not contain foreseeable or potential risks. There are no potential risks from taking part in this study. You may choose not to answer the question that makes you uncomfortable.

Will my information be kept confidential?

The data for this study will be kept confidential to the extent allowed by law. No published results will identify you, and your name will not be associated with the findings. The TAP survey, which is completed through Survey Monkey, is a secured link and will not be linked to the participants' names. The researcher, Luisa Chong, will have access to the data. The study results may be published or presented at professional meetings, but all research participants' identities will remain confidential. The data will be kept for a minimum of 3 years after completing the study as required by CSUF.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study? No

There will be no costs to you for taking part in this study. You will not receive money or any other form of compensation for taking part in this quality improvement project. Upon completing an activity, participant's seven-digit number will be placed in a random drawing for one of four \$25 Amazon gift cards.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher Luisa Chong at (323) 409-6643 or lchong@dhs.lacounty.gov. If you have questions about your rights as a quality improvement participant or would like to report a concern or complaint about the quality improvement activity, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719 or email irb@fullerton.edu.

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this quality improvement project is entirely voluntary. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and or I understand the terms used in this consent form. By clicking agree, I *agree* that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this study.

APPENDIX D

Fishbone Diagram Results

APPENDIX E

SWOT Analysis Diagram Results

Note: Participants' response from two MICU

APPENDIX F

TAP Survey Diagram Results

Note: Participants' response from two MICU

APPENDIX G

Project Recruitment Flyer

Join us to have

ZERO CAUTI_s

(Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections)

Participants needed, sign up ASAP!

Who: Registered Nurses, nursing attendants, and physicians (i.e., attendings, fellows, residents, interns, medical students) working in the Medical Intensive Care Unit 4A and 4B

What:

- ✓ Fishbone
- ✓ Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, & Threats (SWOT) Analysis
- ✓ Targeted Assessment for Prevention (TAP)

When: To be scheduled. Each activity will take approximately 5 to 15 minutes.

Where: Each activity will be available online.

Why: The objectives are to a) identify the underlying causes of CAUTI events, b) identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, and c) identify the level of awareness, knowledge, and perceptions of healthcare personnel related to indwelling urinary catheter practices and CAUTI prevention strategies in two MICUs. Responses to the activities would help provide a better understanding of the practices related to IUC and CAUTI prevention and determine the next steps, such as to determine the best and effective evidence-based strategies that can be tailored to those areas for improvement to reduce CAUTI and improve patient safety and outcomes.

For more details contact: Luisa Chong @ lchong@dhs.lacounty.gov
Infection Prevention/Epidemiology
(323) 409-6643 (office) or (626) 252-2249 (cell)

Upon completing an activity, participants will have an opportunity to be entered in a raffle for a chance to win one of four \$25 Amazon gift cards.
Participate in 3 activities to have more chances to win.
HSR-20-21-155

APPENDIX H

Institute for Healthcare Improvement Framework Use Approval

Permission request: IHI Fishbone

Cayla Saret [REDACTED]

Thu 10/15/2020 2:08 PM

To: Chong, Luisa <LChongDNP@csu.fullerton.edu>

Hello Luisa,

Thank you very much for your patience. I am glad you have found these materials helpful!

IHI is pleased to grant you permission to use the Fishbone diagram for your educational project, provided that the contents are not altered in any way. Please acknowledge IHI as the source of the original material, using the following language: "Reprinted from www.IHI.org with permission of the Institute for Healthcare Improvement, ©2020."

Best,
Cayla

APPENDIX I

Letter of Support from Chief Medical Officer

**Los Angeles County
Board of Supervisors**

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Second District

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Health Services
www.dhs.lacounty.gov

October 15, 2020

Medical Administration
LAC+USC Medical Center
1200 N. State Street
Los Angeles, CA 90033

To the Institutional Review Boards of California State University Fullerton (CSUF):

I am writing this letter at the request of Luisa Chong to confirm that we are working with her as she commences her quality improvement (QI) project, "Decreasing Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections (CAUTI)."

I am aware that she will be conducting three activities: Fishbone and Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, and Threat (SWOT) Analysis sessions, and the Targeted Assessment for Prevention (TAP) survey to determine key areas that need improvement and recommendations will be provided to the stakeholders to reduce CAUTIs. These activities will be conducted among the HCWs who are working in the Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU) at LAC+USC Medical Center. Ms. Chong will have approval to do such procedures for as long as she has the IRB approval.

I also confirm that employees, here at LAC+USC Medical Center, will participate in the recruitment or selection of participants. Staff in the MICU will participate during these activities to identify areas for improvement related to IUC assessment, care, and management and CAUTI prevention. Ms. Chong and her quality improvement team will facilitate personnel to identify priority of areas for improvement of practices to reduce CAUTIs.

If any unanticipated problems or adverse events are to occur, Ms. Chong will report these events to the IRB at CSUF and the LAC+USC Chief Nursing Officer / designee as promptly as possible.

Ms. Chong's QI project will be a valuable contribution to the improvement of our patients, and we will be happy to support her in this endeavor.

Sincerely,

Brad Spellberg, MD
Chief Medical Officer